

Novel Features in Benzyl Chloride/Amine Reaction

P. S. Radhakrishna Murti and G. P. Panigrahi

The kinetics of the reaction of Benzyl chloride with aniline, substituted anilines, β -naphthyl amine and pyridine in 80% nitrobenzene (v/v)-20% alcohol (v/v) is reported. The relative order of the reactivity of the bases is *p*-Toluidine > *m*-Toluidine > Aniline > β -Naphthylamine > *o*-Toluidine > *p*-Chloro aniline > *m*-Chloro aniline. The reaction is inert in pure nitrobenzene medium.

Baker¹ has extensively studied the reaction of benzyl halides with aniline and pyridine in 90% alcohol and established that the primary aromatic amines react faster than tertiary amines like pyridine,

We wish to present some novel features of this reaction of benzyl chloride with aniline, substituted anilines, β -naphthyl amine in pure nitrobenzene medium. The reaction does not occur with primary aromatic amine in this medium but pyridine does react with benzyl chloride in this medium. This is the first report of a reversal of reactivity being observed: pyridine > aromatic primary amines. It appears that the explanation of Baker (loc cit.) to explain the greater reactivity of aromatic amines requires modification. It was explained that attraction of unshared halogen electrons for the positively polarised portion of the attacking aniline molecule is responsible for the enhanced reactivity of primary aromatic amines. It is presumed that the inactivity of the primary aromatic amines in pure nitrobenzene medium may be due to the following four-centered transition state:

It looks as if a hydroxylic solvent is necessary for it to break and yield the products. Pyridine reacts even in nitrobenzene as it is a three-centered process and there is no intramolecular locking up of the leaving group.

To confirm the above, all the primary amines were reacted with benzyl chloride in 80% nitrobenzene -20% ethanol. All of them did react normally. The reactions are simple

1. J. W. Baker. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 2631, 1932.

second order reactions and the reactivity is as follows :

TABLE I

Solvent : Nitrobenzene — Ethanol (80 : 20 v/v) Temperature : 80°

<i>Substrate</i>		<i>K (l.moles⁻¹ min⁻¹)</i>
<i>p</i> -Toluidine01492
<i>m</i> -Toluidine010962
Aniline007548
β -Naphthylamine006605
<i>o</i> -Toluidine004671
<i>p</i> -Chloro aniline0037205
<i>m</i> -Chloro aniline0024306

TABLE II

<i>Substrate:</i> <i>Solvent</i>	<i>Pyridine</i>	<i>Temperature: 80°</i> <i>K (l.moles⁻¹ min⁻¹)</i>
Nitrobenzene (Pure)005755
Nitrobenzene-Ethanol (80: 20 v/v)014436

The order of reactivity even in the mixed solvent is pyridine > aniline, which is against the report made by Baker in 90% alcohol; aniline > pyridine.

Table II indicates that the reaction of pyridine with benzyl chloride in nitrobenzene—ethanol (80:20 v/v) is higher than that in pure nitrobenzene indicating that in the three centred process as postulated for the pyridine benzyl chloride reaction, there is assistance by the hydroxylic solvent for the loss of the leaving group.

The usual corrections for expansion of nitrobenzene and solvolys's of benzyl chloride, if any, were taken into account.

Alternatively the difference in reactivity might be attributed to specific solvent effects and to the difference in the degree of hydration of ions. In an aprotic solvent like nitrobenzene the inactivity is possibly due to difference in ground state and transition state solvation. The transition state stabilisation is certainly high in a protic solvent for these amine reactions and hence higher reactivity.